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CYP2A6 is selectively activated during the first cell division of the human embryo.

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We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation and at the first cell division from 1-cell to 2-cell stage. We describe here discovery/identification of *CYP2A6* as a zygotic cell factor required or important during the first cell division of the fertilized human embryo.

Citations

1. Higashi, E., Fukami, T., Itoh, M., Kyo, S., Inoue, M., Yokoi, T. and Nakajima, M., 2007. Human CYP2A6 is induced by estrogen via estrogen receptor. *Drug Metabolism and Disposition*, 35(10), pp.1935-1941.